

Sol-gel revitalization of porous refractory ceramics

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Abstract: The honeycomb structured supports (Fig. 1) are widely applied in heterogeneous catalysis, in separative processes (filtration, adsorption), etc. If the mentioned porous bodies are manufactured using refractory ceramic precursors (powders) or enter in the refractory state after proceeding, it appears often difficult to fulfil these supports with chemically bonded active components because of their surfaces are drastically deprived from functional active centers being able to be involved into the reactions of ion exchange (for instance, as Bronsted acid (BA) centers $\equiv E-O\cdots H$ acting as H^+ ion exchangers). We suggest applying the sol-gel (SG) method for making the surfaces of refractory porous ceramics highly hydrophilic (Fig. 2) and able to promote the H^+ ion exchange reactions. In particular, it may be seen that several layers of activated alumina $\gamma-Al_2O_3$ (for example – 5) deposited using the SG technics on the surface of a refractory honeycomb lozenge constituted by $\alpha-Al_2O_3$ completely reverse the surface acidity type:

Figure 1. Honeycomb lozenge.

Figure 2. Adsorption isotherms of water vapor at the surface of a virgin refractory honeycomb lozenge constituted by $\alpha-Al_2O_3$ (Fig. 1) and at the lozenges modified with 1, 2 and 3 layers of activated alumina $\gamma-Al_2O_3$; test conditions: temperature – 24.3-24.4 °C, air relative humidity – 34.2-34.7 % (at the left).

Figure 3. Evolution of the pH index in agitated suspensions “water – powdered solid material” [1] (at the right).

the initial refractory surface multi-layered with γ -alumina deposits manifests a domination of BA-centers [1] (Fig. 3) obligatorily required for its efficient chemical modification using some widely used industrial technics, such as wet impregnation in aqueous solutions, epitaxial deposition, CVD-ML (ALD), SG and so on. A variant of the SG method implemented in this work was partially inspired by [2], but the protocol was profoundly revised and simplified. It will be described in details in the final text.

References:

1. Tanabe K., Solid Acids and Bases, *Academic Press*, N.Y.–London, 1970, 175 p.
2. Macedo M.I.F., Osawa C.C., Bertran C.A., *J. Sol-Gel Sci. Techn.*, 2004, **30**, pp. 135-140.

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